

TRANSMISSION PROPERTIES OF ANISOTROPIC PENTAMODE MATERIAL AND FILTERING APPLICATION ON ELASTIC WAVE

Mingye Zheng, E Song & Xiaoning Liu

School of Aerospace Engineering, Beijing Institute of Technology, Beijing, China

Keywords: Transmission properties, Anisotropic pentamode material, Elastic wave, Microstructure

ABSTRACT

Pentamode (PM) materials are degenerated elastic solids which support only one stress state not necessarily hydrostatic, and offer a flexible way to manipulate acoustic wave in liquids. However, the interplay of wave fields between the anisotropic PM material and ordinary solid material is also of great interest and can render the transmission of elastic waves in a more controllable way. In this work, the elastic wave transmission of an anisotropic PM material slab sandwiched in semi-infinite isotropic solids (see Figure 1(a)) are first explored with the parameters running over the full PM material anisotropy and principal orientation. First of all, the continuity conditions of the interface between PM and ordinary solid material is established, then the general transmission property of the above model can be analysed. In Figure 1(b) the contour shows transmissivity of P wave varies with the orientation and degree of anisotropy of the PM slab, which is represented by the ratio of the rigidity of PM material on two principal directions. It is noted that the ratio is not necessarily positive. In particular, a condition for which the wave transmissivity is independent of the frequency is given. The frequency-independent condition can be met by adjusting the anisotropy and orientation of the PM material layer, as illustrated in Figure 1. In figure 1(b), the points on black dashed curve satisfy the frequency-independent condition. Three representative points are selected to validate the previous prediction, in which point A is on the curve, B and C are not on the curve. Figure 1(c) shows the transmissivity of P wave as the function of frequency at A, B and C. It is found that the transmissivity of P wave at point A doesn't vary with the frequency but the other two cases not, especially at point C the transmission of P wave fluctuate drastically against the frequency. And for S wave, there is a similar situation that the transmissivity of S wave at point A doesn't vary with the frequency but the transmission of S wave fluctuate against the frequency at the other two points.

Figure 1: a) Schematic diagram of the model; b) ~ c) Transmission properties;

Further, among the frequency-independent cases, we find that two exclusive filtering cases are of particular interest. For one specific parameter set, P-wave is totally transmitted and S-wave is totally stopped; while for the other case S-wave is fully transmitted and P-wave is fully stopped. The latter case is quite unusual for solid material. To validate the predicted transmitting property, the required PM slab are designed with detailed microstructure (as shown in Figure 2(a)~(c)). The required PM material is realized by honeycomb lattice consisting of slender beams. Figure 2(a) shows the hexagonal unit cell, the beam size and base material can be chosen to match the rigidity and PM feature of the material, and the angle β between the beams dictates the anisotropy, i.e the ratio (s_1/s_2) . Figure 2(b) shows the optimized unit cell, it is noted that since $s_1/s_2 < 0$, the honeycomb lattice is

required to be re-entrant type. Figure 2(c) shows a portion of the expanded PM material lattice. The wave transmitting is validated by the full-wave simulation by using the commercial finite element software COMSOL Multiphysics. Figure 2(d) shows the calculation setup. The model consists of a strip of isotropic material with perfectly connected PM lattice in the middle, and in upper and lower boundary the periodic boundary condition is enforced. Waves are injected from the left side, and on the right side absorbing boundary is established to remove the reflection. Two types of PM lattice layer shown in the figure correspond to the two exclusive filtering cases, respectively.

The displacement fields snapshot at different frequencies corresponding to the two filtering cases are shown in Figure 3. In Figure 3(a), P wave can pass totally and S wave can be almost totally stopped and the results are independent of frequency, which agree very well with previous prediction, while figure 3(b) displays opposite filtering effect.

Figure 2: a) ~ c) Microstructure design of the corresponding PM materials; d) Simulation settings;

Figure 3: a) Numerical simulation of filtering Case 1; b) Numerical simulation of filtering Case 2.

In summary, we studied theoretically and numerically the wave transmission between the PM material and solid material under normal incidence. The effects of anisotropy and orientation of the PM material slab on the transmissivity are thoroughly explored. Since a perfect PM material can only support one type of wave mode, meanwhile the polarization can still possess complexity, the wave transmission might be more effectively manipulated.

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